

STEROID COMPOUNDS. PART I. A SYNTHESIS OF DESOXY-TESTOSTERONE*

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A synthesis of desoxy-testosterone is described.

The synthesis of alicyclic rings related to sex-hormones, sterols and bile acids has engaged the attention of chemists ever since the structures of the natural products were established. Besides the synthesis of equilin and an isomer of oestrone (Bachmann *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 824; 1942, 64, 974) the synthesis of products belonging to this class, which are derived from *cyclopentano-perhydrophenanthrene* (I) ring system, remained a serious problem for synthetic organic chemists. One of the features of these compounds, which has been a formidable obstacle in the synthetic path, is the presence of angular methyl groups between the rings A-B and C-D of the steroid skeleton. Quite recently, Martin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 491) have synthesised a stereoisomer or a mixture of stereoisomers of androstendione, which is the first successful synthesis of a *cyclopentano-perhydrophenanthrene* derivative.;

The ingenious method developed by Mcquillin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53) for the synthesis of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated cyclic ketones containing an angular methyl group by condensing the methiodides of "Mannich" bases with cyclic ketones containing a keto-methin ($-\text{CO}-\text{CHCH}_3-$) group, offers best promise of success for the synthesis of non-benzenoid steroids of testosterone type. An application of this method to tricyclic ketones of the type (II), permits the synthesis of testosterone (III, R-OH) and cholestenone (III, R-*sec*-isooctyl), provided the corresponding tricyclic ketones (II, R-OH; *sec*-isooctyl) are available (Robinson *et al.*, *loc. cit.* Robinson and Weygand, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 386). An attempt to build up the steroid skeleton by the above method therefore requires a convenient route to the tricyclic ketones of the type (II). Synthetic methods towards this end are, however, very limited and the methods so far successfully developed involve hydrogenation of suitable hydroaromatic derivatives.

* A preliminary note was published in *Science & Culture*, 1945-46, 11, 574.

: In a very recent publication (Cornforth and Robinson; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 676) it has been pointed out that "the attempt of Martin and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) to synthesise a stereoisomeride of androstendione broke down at the last stage, because the addition of a ring to BCD intermediate did not proceed so as to give ABCD which should have been structurally identical with androstendione, but afforded BCDE."

In the present communication is described a method that has been developed for the synthesis of tricyclic ketones of the type (II), which offers the possibility of application in the synthesis of *cyclopentano-perhydrophenanthrene* with the angular methyl groups and the side-chain characteristic of natural sterols. As a preliminary, the synthesis of 2:5-dimethyl-1:2-*cyclopentano-perhydronaphthalene-6-one* (II, R-H) has been successfully carried out and from this the tetracyclic ketone, desoxytestosterone (III, R-H) has been obtained by an application of Robinson's "Mannich" base method.

The starting point of the present investigation is ethyl 2-methylcyclopentanone-2- β -propionate (IV), which has been prepared from methyl cyclopentanone and ethyl β -bromopropionate. The above keto-ester (IV) has been condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate according to the method of Cope (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452) to yield the unsaturated cyano-ester (V). Reduction of the above unsaturated ester with aluminium amalgam affords the saturated cyano-ester (VI) in an excellent yield, the potassium salt of which condenses smoothly with ethyl β -bromopropionate to yield the glutarate (VII). This has been hydrolysed by prolonged boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid to the tricarboxylic acid (VIII, R-H); the triethyl ester (VIII, R-Et) of this acid smoothly undergoes Dieckmann's condensation in presence of sodium dust. The resulting β -keto ester has been hydrolysed with 20% H_2SO_4 to the keto-acid (IX, R-R'-H) which affords the keto-ester (IX, R-Et; R'-H). This keto-ester is then reacted with activated zinc and ethyl- α -bromopropionate and the crude condensation product is hydrolysed with alcoholic caustic potash, when the unsaturated tricyclic ketone (X) is obtained on diluting the alkaline solution with water. The cyclisation during Reformatsky's reaction, observed here, is in harmony with the similar results recorded by Adamson, Mcquillin, Robinson and Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1576). The unsaturated ketone on hydrogenation in presence of Adam's catalyst in alcohol furnishes the saturated ketone (II, R-H). This tricyclic ketone is next condensed with the methiodide of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one under usual conditions (Martin and Robinson, *loc. cit.* Ghosh and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 506) and the higher boiling product obtained has been found from the analytical data to be a mixture of the desired tetracyclic ketone (III, R-H) and the intermediate diketone (XI). It is treated with dry sodium methoxide in benzene solution and the neutral product on

sublimation in *vacuo* affords the tetracyclic ketone (III, R-H) as a pale yellow highly viscous oil.

An extension of the above reactions to 2-methyl-3-*isooctylcyclopentanone* (Mukherjee, *Science & Culture*, 1911-42, 7, 58) will eventually lead to the formation of a compound possessing cholestenone structure and this work is in progress.

It may be of interest to point out here that the problem of the construction of natural steroid skeletons becomes much simplified if a convenient simpler route to 0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane derivatives of the type IX (R = Et; R' = substituent) is worked out. The condensation of substituted 2-methylcyclopentanones e.g., 2-methyl-3-*isooctylcyclopentanone* and related compounds, with the methiodide of (Et)₂N·CH₂CH₂COCH₂CH₂CH₂CO₂Et in presence of sodamide appears to be a very attractive route to bicyclic systems of the type (IX). Work along this line is well under way and the results will be the subject matter of a future communication. Other routes to the derivatives of this important intermediate (IX) are also being investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl 2-Methylcyclopentanone-2β-propionate (IV).—A mixture of *ortho*-methylcyclopentanone (49 g.), powdered sodamide (21 g.) in dry ether (800 c. c.) was stirred under reflux for 5 hours. The volume of ether was then reduced to 300 c. c. (Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 649) and ethyl β-bromopropionate (93 g.) was added to the above sodio salt cooled in ice in course of 20 minutes with constant stirring. After addition was complete the temperature was gradually raised and the ethereal solution refluxed for 3 hours. It was then decomposed with ice and ethereal layer separated, washed with water and dried. After removal of the solvent the residue was distilled and the fraction boiling at 125-145°/10 mm. as a colourless mobile liquid (40 g.) was collected. A higher boiling residue was left in the flask which was not investigated.

A mixture of the above condensation product (40 g.) and ethyl oxalate (29.5 g.) cooled in a freezing mixture was gradually added to a solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (46 g.) in alcohol (60 c. c.), similarly cooled in a freezing mixture (-20°) with constant shaking and the mixture left overnight in the freezing bath, tightly corked. The red solution was next poured into cold water and extracted with ether and the ethereal layer separated. The alkaline solution was next acidified and the precipitated oil extracted with ether.

The crude oxalyl derivative, obtained on removal of ether, was then hydrolysed with baryta (134 g.) and water (670 c. c.) for 3 hours when the oil completely passed into solution. It was extracted with ether to remove any neutral matter that might be present and the alkaline solution then acidified and repeatedly extracted with ether and the crude acid, obtained on the removal of solvent, was esterified with alcohol (100 c.c.) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (6 c. c.) for 15 hours. The ester was worked up in the usual way and distilled at 130°/9 mm. as a colourless mobile liquid, yield 30 g. (Found: C, 66.31; H, 8.96. C₁₁H₁₈O₃ requires C, 66.67; H, 9.1 per cent). The

semicarbazone crystallised from dilute methanol as small needles, m. p. 80-81°. (Found : C, 55.9 ; H, 8.08. $C_{12}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires C, 56.47 ; H, 8.23 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Methyl-2-β-carbomethoxyethylcyclopentylidenecyanoacetate (V).—The above keto-ester (50 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (30 g.), ammonium acetate (5 g.), glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) in benzene (100 c.c.) were refluxed for 10 hours in a flask fitted with a water separator (*cf. Cope et al., loc. cit.*). The benzene solution was then repeatedly washed with water and the benzene removed under reduced pressure. The residue was fractionated and the unsaturated cyano-ester (25 g.) collected at 174°/2.5 mm. as a pale yellow viscous liquid. (Found : C 65.8 ; H, 8.0. $C_{16}H_{23}O_4N$ requires C, 65.5 ; H, 7.85 per cent).

The low boiling fractions containing the unchanged keto-ester and cyanoacetic ester were again treated as before when a further quantity (13 g.) of the unsaturated cyano-ester was obtained. During this condensation with recovered materials a crystalline solid distilling between 150° and 160°/2.5 mm. was obtained as a byproduct, the amount of which increased considerably when a third condensation with recovered materials was attempted. The character of this abnormal product is under investigation.

Ethyl 2-Methyl-2-β-carbomethoxyethylcyclopentylcyanacetate (VI).—The above unsaturated cyano-ester (35 g.), aluminium amalgam (prepared from 30 g of aluminium foil), rectified spirit (2 c.c.) in moist ether (500 c.c.) were left at the ordinary temperature for 7 days. The ethereal solution together with the aluminium sludge was cooled in a freezing mixture and then poured into ice-hydrochloric acid mixture (Bagchi and Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 377). The ethereal layer separated and the aqueous solution extracted with ether. The combined ethereal extracts were washed with water, dilute bicarbonate solution and dried. The residue left on removal of the ether was distilled and the saturated cyano-ester (30g.) collected at 157-59°/2 mm. as a colourless mobile liquid. (Found : C. 65.8 ; H, 8.5. $C_{16}H_{23}O_4N$ requires C. 65.1 ; H, 8.5 per cent).

Ethyl α-Cyano-α-(2-methyl-2-β-carbomethoxyethylcyclopentyl) glutarate (VII).—Ethyl β-bromopropionate (18 g.) was added to the potassio derivative of the above cyanoacetic ester (VI), prepared from potassium (3.7 g.), cyano-ester (28 g) and xylene (100 c.c.). The reaction mixture was left overnight, then heated on the water-bath for 4 hours and finally refluxed in an oil-bath for 6 hours. The reaction product was worked up in the usual way and distilled, b.p. 195-97°/3 mm., yield 24 g. (Found : C, 64.2 ; H, 8.33. $C_{21}H_{29}O_6N$ requires C, 63.8 ; H, 8.35 per cent).

Ethyl α-(2-Methyl-2-β-carbomethoxyethylcyclopentyl) glutarate (VIII, R = Et).—The above substituted cyano-ester (23 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with concentrated hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.) for 70 hours, when the tribasic acid (VIII, R = H) was obtained as white shining crystals together with an adhering gum. It was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid, m.p. 170-72°. (Found : C, 58.2 ; H, 8.0. $C_{14}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 58.74 ; H, 7.7 per cent).

The tricarboxylic acid was then esterified with alcohol (60. c.c.) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (9 c.c.) for 30 hours and the ester worked up in the usual way and distilled, b.p. 166-68°/2.5 mm., yield 17g. (Found : C, 64.36 ; H, 8.98. $C_{20}H_{34}O_6$ requires C, 64.86 ; H, 9.19 per cent).

Ethyl 8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-5-one-4-β-propionate (IX, R = Et ; R' = H) — The above pimelate (16 g.) was refluxed with sodium dust (2 g.) in benzene (80 c.c.) until the whole of the sodium had reacted. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer separated. The benzene solution was washed with dilute bicarbonate solution, then with water and dried. Benzene was removed under diminished pressure and the β-keto ester distilled, b.p. 157-59°/3 mm. (Found : C, 66.3 ; H, 8.56. $C_{14}H_{28}O_5$ requires C, 66.66 ; H, 8.64 per cent). The β-keto ester gave an intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The β-keto ester was hydrolysed by refluxing with 20% sulphuric acid (150 c.c.) for 30 hours in an oil-bath. The acid (IX, R = R' = H) was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue left on removal of ether was thoroughly dried in vacuum and esterified with alcohol (75 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (4 c.c.) for 20 hours. The keto-ester was worked up in the usual way and distilled, b.p. 144-46°/3.5 mm., yield 8 g. (Found : C, 70.6 ; H, 9.47. $C_{15}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 71.4 ; H, 9.5 per cent).

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual way, was obtained in silky needles from dilute alcohol, m. p. 158-60°. (Found : C, 62.26 ; H, 9.1. $C_{18}H_{27}O_3N_3$ requires C, 62.14 ; H, 8.73 per cent).

2 : 5-Dimethyl-1 : 2-cyclopentano $\Delta^{5:10}$ -octahydronaphthalene-6-one (X). — The above keto-ester (7.5 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of thiophene-free benzene (16 c.c.), activated zinc (2 g.), ethyl α-bromopropionate (5.5 g.) and a crystal of iodine. A vigorous reaction set in within 15 minutes and the whole of the zinc passed into solution within one hour. The heating was continued for 1 hour more and the product decomposed with iced dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with benzene, washed with dilute ammonia and water. The residue left on the removal of benzene was then hydrolysed with 10% alcoholic KOH (7.5 g.) solution for 2 hours and the alkaline solution poured into water when an oil separated which was repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the ether, a brown oil with a very characteristic odour was obtained. It distilled at 139-140°/3 mm. as a pale yellow oil, yield 2.5 g. (Found : C, 81.82, 82.34 ; H ; 10.10, 9.9. $C_{15}H_{22}O$ requires C, 82.56 ; H, 10.1 per cent).

The unsaturated ketone furnished a semicarbazone instantaneously in the cold which crystallised from alcohol in minute shining crystals, m. p. 207°. (Found : C, 69.8 ; H, 9.2. $C_{16}H_{25}ON_3$ requires C, 69.8 ; H, 9.1 per cent).

The alkaline solution was acidified, extracted with ether and the acid esterified to yield the unreacted keto-ester (IX). This yielded a further quantity of

the unsaturated ketone (1.2 g.) on treatment with zinc and ethyl α -bromopropionate.

2 : 5-Dimethyl-1 : 2-cyclopentanoperhydroaphthalene-6-one (II, R = H).—The unsaturated ketone (3.2 g.) was hydrogenated over Adam's catalyst (0.2 g.) until one mole of hydrogen had been absorbed (3 hours). The alcoholic solution was filtered off from the catalyst and the saturated ketone distilled, b. p. 132-33°/3 mm. A small quantity of a higher boiling product was left in the flask which was not investigated. The saturated ketone was obtained as a colourless viscous oil possessing a very sweet odour resembling "Khus". (Found : C, 81.3 ; H, 10.9. $C_{15}H_{24}O$ requires C, 81.8 ; H, 10.9 per cent).

The ketone furnished a semicarbazone readily in the cold which after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 224°. (Found : C, 69.32 ; H, 9.3. $C_{15}H_{27}ON_3$ requires C, 69.31 ; H, 9.7 per cent).

Desoxy-testosterone (III, R = H).—The above tricyclic ketone (2.2 g.), powdered sodamide (0.5 g.) and ether (40 c. c.) were stirred under nitrogen at room temperature for 5 hours, then cooled in ice while a solution of 4 diethylaminobutan-2-one (from 1.8 g. of base) in alcohol (12 c. c.) was added in the course of 10 minutes. Stirring continued in the cold for 3 hours, then at the ordinary temperature for another 2 hours and the mixture left overnight in an atmosphere of nitrogen. It was then refluxed for 1 hour, cooled and poured into ice-hydrochloric acid mixture and the product isolated with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dilute NaOH solution and again with water. After drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the solvent was removed and the residue distilled. At first the unreacted ketone (1 g.) distilled at 110-140°/1 mm. (bath temp.) followed by a fraction which distilled at 160-170°/0.1 mm. (bath temp.) as a yellow glass. (Found : C, 79.9, 79.8 ; H, 9.9, 10.1. $C_{19}H_{28}O$ requires C, 83.8 ; H, 10.29. $C_{19}H_{30}O_2$ requires C, 78.6 ; H, 10.9 per cent).

The substance was obviously a mixture of the required tetracyclic compound and the intermediate diketone (XI). It was next treated with dry sodium methoxide (0.1 g.) in benzene (30 c. c.) and left overnight. Next day it was heated at 60° for 1 hour and poured into cold water. Benzene layer was separated, washed with water and the residue left on removal of benzene was sublimed and a fraction boiling at 150-155°/0.08 mm. (bath temp.) as a pale yellow highly viscous oil was collected. (Found : C, 83.14 ; H, 10.18. $C_{19}H_{28}O$ requires C, 83.8 ; H, 10.29 per cent).

The author is grateful to Prof. P. C. Mitter for his valuable advice and encouragement during the course of this investigation and for the facilities provided ; to Prof. S. N. Bose for his keen interest and valuable criticism ; to Dr. D. K. Banerjee for his advice and generous help throughout the investigation ; to Dr. P. C. Dutta for a gift of the starting materials and to Mr. N. Ghosh, M. Sc. for the micro-analysis of most of the compounds.

